

1 Exploring Selected Maps in the Stop Cop City 2 Movement

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8 **Abstract**

9 This short paper explores cartographic technologies and techniques used to produce online maps
10 that communicate geospatial information about a proposed police training facility in the South River
11 Forest in Atlanta, Georgia. The proposed facility has spurred an activist movement in opposition to
12 the plans, known as the Stop Cop City and/or Defend the Atlanta Forest movements. We gather
13 a set of publicly available government maps, media articles, and user-generated content (UGC)
14 that we discovered through Internet searches. We find that most maps focused on the division of
15 the proposed project site into various uses per the site plan. We also find that members of the
16 public who opposed the project typically annotated existing maps. Absent from these maps are
17 facts surrounding the site as Indigenous land, and statistical data, such as Census data. In general,
18 we argue that documenting the use of maps in a decentralized social movement can help assess the
19 value of (and varied access to) geospatial technologies for communicating information, positions,
20 and perspectives about community issues.

21 **2012 ACM Subject Classification** Human-centered computing → Geographic visualization

22 **Keywords and phrases** Social movements, activist communities, maps, cartography, GIS

23 **1 Introduction**

24 Atlanta, Georgia (metropolitan area population: 4,515,419 (2020 U.S. Census)) is a city
25 in the U.S. South that serves as the main industrial and technological economic engine for
26 the region. Atlanta is also a historically majority Black city with notable Black history.
27 Often called the “Cradle of the Civil Rights Movement,” Atlanta is home to many significant
28 moments and locations of the Civil Rights Movement in the 1960s, including home to Dr.
29 Martin Luther King Jr.’s Ebenezer Baptist Church. Racial disparities in the city remain to
30 date. In terms of natural resources, Atlanta is known as the “City in the Forest” in reference
31 to its ample but endangered tree canopy [6]. Atlanta is one of the country’s most vulnerable
32 cities to climate change, with the tree canopy or “lungs of Atlanta” considered crucial for
33 preventing some of the most harmful impacts of climate change [11].

34 In 2017, the City of Atlanta released official plans to build a police training facility
35 on a 321 acre plot of forested land in the South River Forest in Atlanta. Communities of
36 activists and residents have collectively opposed this plan as part of the nationally-recognized
37 Stop Cop City (SCC) and/or the Defend the Atlanta Forest Movement. This movement
38 integrates issues of racial justice, environmental impacts, climate change, and over-policing,
39 in its opposition to the development project [1, 10, 14]. Alongside photos, videos, articles,
40 and artistic media, maps about the facility made by officials and the opposition movement
41 continue to circulate on the web.

42 Using the research framework of *critical cartography* surrounding social movements [5, 8, 7],
43 we explore the maps shared by key players in this conflict. *Critical cartography* focuses on
44 subjectivity in maps with an emphasis on power dynamics [17] to highlight who has power
45 in the construction of maps, strategies used to communicate messages through mapping,

46 intentional inclusion and exclusion of features, and how maps are used to justify decisions
47 [4, 9, 18, 5]. In this short position paper, our goal is to describe which geo-visualization
48 strategies, data, and map styles are used to communicate messages to the public about
49 the training facility’s benefits and risks, and what kinds of data and messages are omitted.
50 We search for maps related to the training facility and the SCC movement through search
51 engines and Twitter, tag maps with commonly-used cartographic keywords sourced from
52 textbooks, and report on commonalities and rarities in the collection of maps.

53 The contribution of this work is a description of narratives, perspectives, and technological
54 choices of community members, journalists, and government officials who create and share
55 maps about a controversial topic.

56 **2 Background: Police Training Facility and Opposition**

57 The City of Atlanta, together with the Atlanta Police Foundation (APF), plans to build the
58 training site on a 321 acre parcel outside the city limits, inside DeKalb County, Georgia [16].
59 The site’s infrastructure will include simulations of city buildings (such as a nightclub and
60 a convenience store), animal stables, a shooting range, and administrative buildings. The
61 project has an estimated cost of \$90 million USD [14].

62 The location of the facility in the South River Forest has raised concerns that the
63 destruction of the large forest will exacerbate extreme heat and flooding and reduce green
64 space for recreation for locals [11, 13]. According to the official cultural impact assessments,
65 the site is known for its history as a prison farm, where incarcerated individuals, particularly
66 Black men, were forced to work on the farm [12, 10].

67 There is no central organization spearheading the Stop Cop City / Defend the Atlanta
68 Forest opposition movement. As Akbar writes, it is not an organization, but “a loosely
69 affiliated group of autonomous individuals, protecting the land against encroachment and
70 seemingly motivated by anarchist principles” [1, p. 64]. The movement escalated in January
71 2023 after law enforcement shot and killed activist Manuel Paez Teran in the South River
72 Forest [10] and subsequently, activists responded with street protests, vigils, concerts (which
73 have, collectively, resulted in 40+ arrests) and most recently, the launch of an effort to force
74 a legal referendum.

75 **3 Data and Methods**

76 **3.1 Mapping Data Acquisition**

77 We collected images of maps and interactive maps from websites and reports that we found
78 through Google searches and Google Image searches (<http://images.google.com>). We used
79 the search phrases: ‘Cop City’, ‘Stop Cop City’, ‘Atlanta Public Safety Training Center’,
80 ‘Atlanta Police Training Facility’, each followed by the word ‘map’. We also performed
81 searches on Twitter using the same keywords. Searches were performed between May and
82 August, 2023¹.

83 We searched Twitter by entering the terms into the Twitter search bar and selecting the
84 Media tab and the Top tab. The Top tab returned the most popular results containing the

¹ Due to the deprecation of the Twitter API for academic use, we were unable to access content programmatically from Twitter.

85 keywords, and the Media tab returned all results containing an image or video and the search
86 term. Both searches return results in order of recency.

87 We also analyzed authoritative cartographic documents in this project, including an
88 environmental impact study (EIS), cultural impact assessment found on the official APF
89 website².

90 3.2 Analysis

91 To analyze maps we use a set of keywords found in geovisualization and cartography textbooks
92 (e.g., [15]). For instance, we use cartography terms such as: **reference map, thematic**
93 **map, choropleth map, outlines, icons, polygons** and map elements such as **scale**
94 **bar, north arrow, legend** and **inset map** and keywords from the U.S. National Archives
95 **topographic, aerial, relief, and land use** [2]. We use keywords that describe visual
96 variables such as: **color, size, and transparency** [3] and reference visual features such
97 as **target** shapes. We organize and clean the keywords in the R Statistical Computing
98 Environment. We also create a set of higher level themes from the keywords. We tally the
99 total frequency of these keywords into a tables and provide a descriptive analysis of the
100 results and our interpretation.

101 When the software used to create the maps (e.g., Datawrapper, ArcGIS) is evident (via a
102 written reference or our observational knowledge), we also report on the results in a table.
103 We list data sources when available and note trends in UGC methods (e.g., annotation or
104 screencapping).

105 4 Results

106 In total we retrieved 38 unique cartographic images, including annotated aerial photos (i.e.,
107 orthorectified imagery with graphics or freehand mouse-drawn drawings), and one map from
108 the EIS document that was retrieved through the search. We remove 11 annotated aerial
109 photos / annotated maps (e.g., Figure 1), two annotated graphics that were not designed
110 with the topic in mind (e.g., a map of ZIP codes), and a map that was created before the
111 conflict began. For the keyword analysis, we study 24 maps (including two interactive maps
112 ^{3,4}) (Table 1) most of which were sourced from news articles.

113 We annotated maps with 115 unique keywords and 266 total keywords (see Appendix).
114 The keywords were organized into 24 high level themes (Table 2). The most common themes
115 were the detection of map elements, colors (especially green, red, and blue), areas (such as
116 drawn polygons of the lot), hydrological features, roads, and civic elements such as schools
117 and basemaps.

118 The maps we retrieved were largely reference maps. Differences in map projections were
119 not evident. Many maps had a scale bar (41.6%), inset map(s) (37.5%), labels (33.3%),
120 legend (29.2%) and a north arrow (16.6%). These elements suggest that map makers have
121 some background or training in cartography; this is unsurprising since much of our content
122 is from news articles. The most common feature were polygons that represented an enclosed
123 area, followed by roads (37.5%). Very few maps did not include context or a basemap (e.g.,
124 Figure 2), and many included aerial imagery (satellite photos, etc.) in the background
125 (26.1%).

² <https://atlantapolicefoundation.org/programs/public-safety-training-center/>

³ <https://www.stopcopcitysolidarity.org/targets>

⁴ <https://atlprescollective.com/2023/03/04/land-swap-or-cop-city-a-guide/>

■ **Table 1** Data Sources for Keyword Analysis, Sorted Ascending by Publication Date

No.	Publication & Author (Hyper-linked)	Data Sources, Software, Primary Sources	Publication Date
1	Terracon	Various Sources	Apr 22, 2021
2	Defend the Atlanta Forest (@defendatlforest)	<i>None stated</i>	May 13, 2021
3	Mainlinezine, By Wayne Butler	USGS StreamStats, APF Data	Jul 14, 2021
4	Mainlinezine, By Wayne Butler	USGS StreamStats	Jul 14, 2021
5	Urbanize Atlanta, By Josh Green	Atlanta Police Foundation	Aug 25, 2021
6	Atlanta Journal Constitution, By Anjali Huynh	Atlanta Police Foundation	Aug 10, 2021
7	The Appeal, By Aja Arnold	<i>None stated</i>	Dec 08, 2021
8-10	Atlanta Community Press Collective (@atlanta_press)	Dekalb County Property Information Website, Google Sheets	May 11, 2022
11	Capital B News, By Adam Mahoney and Adjoa Danso	Datawrapper	Jun 6, 2022
12	The Atlanta Journal-Constitution, By Tyler Estep, Map: Hannah Ziegler	OpenStreetMap, Datawrapper	Aug 12, 2022
13, 14	CNN, By Christina Maxouris, Map: Renee Rigdon	South River Forest Coalition, Atlanta Police Foundation, Google	Sep 24, 2022
15	StopCopCitySolidarity.org via RAM INC (@resistabolish)	Leaflet, uMap, Django, OpenStreetMap	Jan 25, 2023
16	Axios, By Emma Hurt	City of Atlanta	Feb 1, 2023
17	Saporta Report, By John Ruch	Affidavit of R. Baskin, Atlanta Police Foundation	Mar 1, 2023
18	Atlanta Community Press Collective	Datawrapper	Mar 4, 2023
19	National Public Radio, By Bill Chappell	City of Atlanta	Mar 7, 2023
20	Inside Climate News, By Victoria St. Martin, Map: Paul Horn	Atlanta Community Press Collective, Atlanta Police Foundation, ESRI	Mar 8, 2023
21	FOX 5 Atlanta Digital Team	Atlanta Police Department	May 30, 2023
22	Mapping Atlanta, By Taylor Shelton	QGIS	May 30, 2023
23	The Xylem, By Alex Ip (@AlexIp718)	Datawrapper	Aug 2, 2023
24	Atlanta Police Foundation	<i>None stated</i>	N.D.

■ **Figure 1** Annotated imagery with graphics atop the APF’s rendering of the training facility area. Source: Save The Old Atlanta Prison Farm, Posted on *Facebook*, April 30, 2021.

■ **Figure 2** A map of the facility’s different segments, without peripheral context. Source: Josh Green, *Urbanize Atlanta*, Aug 10, 2021.

■ **Figure 3** The official Public Safety Training Center Plan. Source: *Atlanta Police Foundation*, No date.

126 **4.1 Three Examples**

127 The “official map” of the facility shared by the Atlanta Police Foundation has hand-drawn
 128 artistic elements that are rendered to appear 3D, including lush green trees and green areas,
 129 buildings, trails and water bodies (Figure 3). The map does not contain the traditional map
 130 elements described above, but has labels for Key Road, the Metro Detention Center and
 131 Intrinchement Creek. The trees are made to appear textured and almost ‘fluffy’, to give the
 132 map a soft look. The local area is faded to de-emphasize the surroundings.

133 The map entitled “**A Fight Over South River Forest**” is an example of a journalistic
 134 map with common map elements and landmarks (Figure 4). However, the area where the
 135 police training facility will be built is still shaded with (light) green with the term ‘green
 136 space’ written across it and adjacent properties. The map appears to use a basemap, which
 137 constrains what is shown in the background. The map includes footprints of interior site
 138 elements, such as the jogging track, to help readers envision what is proposed to be built
 139 inside the plot.

140 One map that was not affiliated with large media outlets was “**Cop City Connections**” a
 141 map of the locations of individuals’ homes who are “connected to the institutions responsible
 142 for Cop City” (Figure 5). In this map, the mapmaker chose a black background and a target
 143 as stylistic elements, and uses a network of nodes and edges to show connections of affiliates

■ **Figure 4** “A Fight over South River Forest” shows a balanced view of the facility and contextual landmarks using classic map elements. Source: Paul Horn, *Inside Climate News*, Mar 8, 2023.

■ **Figure 5** “Cop City Connections” is a map connecting the home locations of those affiliated with the project to the site using lines. Source: Taylor Shelton, *Mapping Atlanta*, May, 30 2023.

144 to the facility. The map uses cumulative negative space to direct the eye to a cluster of
 145 households that are northwest of the site. It provides little context, but instead focuses on
 146 the dispersion of the connections from the site.

147 4.2 Technology

148 In terms of technology, we found that users against Cop City often annotated aerial photos or
 149 pre-existing maps using mouse-drawn outlines, points, lines, etc. (e.g. Figure 6). Individuals
 150 may annotate within a map environment, such as the DeKalb County Parcel Viewer (Figure
 151 7), or use other graphics or GIS software to make these annotations. Along with uncertainty
 152 in software usage, it is unclear where mapmakers sourced their data. In addition, a number
 153 of maps were created with Datawrapper. This free, online visualization software is popular
 154 among leading news outlets (e.g., The Washington Post and The New York Times). However,
 155 it is not a traditional GISystem, and does not allow for map analysis. Conversely, maps used
 156 in the EIS documents and in official legal documents from the APF used professional GIS
 157 software that allows for statistical analysis (such as Esri ArcMap, which was likely used to
 158 create Figure 8).

159 4.3 Interpretations

160 We found that pictorial icons were rare, but seemed to be a source of creative expression,
 161 such as the clapboard from an interactive map from the Atlanta Press Collective (Figure 9).
 162 We also noted a lack of Indigenous mapping on these maps, although the forest was once
 163 called the Muscogee Weelaunee Forest and was home to the Muscogee Creek people [14]. We
 164 also noted that mapmakers did not use statistical quantitative data. Thus, map style choices
 165 such as cartograms, dot density maps, and techniques such as data binning methods and the
 166 use of color ramps, etc. could not be analyzed.

167 Accordingly, the maps do not communicate information about the people who are affected
 168 by the facility. Furthermore, potential environmental issues were rarely illustrated on maps,

■ **Figure 6** “South River Forest Under Threat” uses primary colors and transparency to show segments of the training area (in blue) and surrounding land. Retrieved from Twitter, @defendATLforest, May 13, 2021.

■ **Figure 7** The DeKalb County Parcel Viewer allows users to annotate maps, which allows users to emphasize parts of the map and export the results. Screen capture from <https://dekalbgis.maps.arcgis.com>.

169 although one article that opposed the facility used a USGS StreamStats model to show
 170 that runoff entering the local tributary ran through the planned explosives testing site and
 171 shooting range (Figure 10).

■ **Figure 8** “Atlanta Public Safety Training Campus” uses gem colors and transparency to show segments of the parcels involved in the training campus and surrounding land. Source: APF, via John Rush, *Saporta Report*, Mar 1, 2023.

■ **Figure 9** This interactive map entitled “Land Swap or Cop City?: A Visual Guide” uses neon hatches and icons to guide users through parts of the site. Source: *Atlanta Community Press Collective*, Mar 4, 2023.

172 5 Discussion and Conclusion

173 In summary, we searched Google Images, Google, and Twitter using four phrases to download
 174 cartographic media on the topic of the Stop Cop City Movement. We discovered a wide
 175 variety in mapping strategies, but the focus was typically on the site and how it was divided
 176 into areas (the training center, green space, etc.). We did not find evidence of spatial analysis
 177 or thematic mapping, and many of the maps’ goals seemed to be to show the reader the plans
 178 for the land in a “legal” way. A few maps emphasized the shooting range and coincidence

■ **Figure 10** APF plans overlaid atop USGS StreamStats (an online GIS modeling tool) data on paths of runoff (in red) from the shooting range (labeled). Source: Wayne Butler, *Mainlinezine*, Jul 14, 2021.

179 with the local watershed to argue against the facility.

180 Our study has multiple limitations. First, this exploration does not measure the impact
 181 of such maps. We did not count how often maps were shared or liked on social media, or the
 182 presence of the same map across multiple articles or posts.

183 Next, choosing keywords and high level themes for the maps (e.g, “neighborhood”,
 184 “highway”) was subjective and prone to human error. In the future, we plan to create a
 185 pre-defined set of keywords to eliminate semantic duplication, typographic errors, and too
 186 coarse or fine grained keywords. In the future, we plan to ask multiple coders to assign each
 187 keyword a higher level theme.

188 In terms of the mapmaker’s choices, many maps used basemaps, which made it difficult
 189 to analyze which features and symbology were important. For instance, some basemaps
 190 showed Intrenchment Creek, but others did not; this may or may not have aligned with the
 191 mapmakers intentions.

192 In addition, this study covers a limited sample of maps (although we found many maps
 193 repeated in our multiple searches). The authors know of multiple maps and cartographic
 194 resources that were shared in February on Twitter, but due to the many SCC-related posts
 195 in 2023 and limited number of tweets returned for each of our keywords, these maps were
 196 not retrieved nor part of our study. Accordingly, this case illustrates the need for academic
 197 researchers to have access to APIs for Tweets. In the future, we plan to search for more
 198 UGC and examples from the EIS and other legal documents.

199 In summary, maps are not to be understood as neutral communication devices, and
 200 they have social consequences and implications. Inquiring about the technology, data and
 201 approaches used in mapping and counter-mapping in the Stop Cop City movement can tell us
 202 more about what map strategies are used for these exercises and what cartographic choices
 203 not just *are* being made but what *can* be made, given the limitations of these tools and
 204 the mapmakers’ experience. This particular exercise illustrated a generally balanced map
 205 making strategy by the media, while the government used lush renderings and artistic work,
 206 and dissenting opinions often annotated existing media. In the future, we hope to gather a
 207 wider swath of maps, interview mapmakers, and share this consolidated collection of maps

■ **Table 2** Count of Keywords by Coded High-Level Theme.

Theme	Count of Appearances	Distinct Keywords	Example Keyword
Map Element	60	14	Number Labels
Color	33	12	Green
Area	27	5	Footprints
Civic	20	11	Airport
Style	17	7	Artist Rendering
Basemap/Background	14	6	Basemap
Water	14	10	Constitution Lake
Green space	13	9	Gresham Park
Infrastructure	11	3	Highways
Administrative	9	5	Canada
Government	7	3	EIS
Map Capability	6	3	Interactive Map
Lot/Land/Tax	5	5	Cadastral Data
Nature	5	2	Trails
Danger	4	3	At Risk Area
Distance	4	1	Euc. Dist. Target
Clip Art	3	3	Clapboard
Data Type	3	2	CAD
Facility	3	2	Cop City
Geometry	3	3	Lines
Land Use	2	2	Housing
Individual	2	1	Millsap
Addresses	1	1	Home Locations

208 with the public.

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252 **6 Appendix**

■ **Table 3** Top Individual Keywords with Three or More Appearances in the Coded Map Data

Keyword	Appearances	Keyword (cont.)	Appearances
Polygons	11	Basemap	4
Scale Bar	10	Faded	4
Inset Map	9	Footprints	4
Roads	9	Icons	4
Green	8	North Arrow	4
Labels	8	Number Labels	4
Red	8	Parcels	4
Aerial Imagery	7	School	4
Legend	7	Target	4
Partial Transparency	6	Old Prison Farm	3
Variety of Uses Inside Polygon	6	Shooting Range	3
Blue	5	Trees	3
Government Tool	5	Youth Detention Center	3
Shaded Relief	5		